

Ion-Solvent Interaction and Solvation Numbers of Alkali Metal Nitrates in Dimethyl Sulfoxide at 25°C

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Manuscript received 2 January 1979, revised 16 October 1979, accepted 25 August 1980

The Fuoss-Onsager-Skinner Conductance Equation has been used to analyse high precision conductance data of alkali metal nitrates in DMSO at 25°. The association constants calculated are in the order $\text{NaNO}_3 > \text{KNO}_3 > \text{RbNO}_3 > \text{CsNO}_3 > \text{LiNO}_3$. The sizes of the solvodynamic units have been estimated by the Nightingale method. Solvation numbers of the ions are Li^+ 4.3, Na^+ 3.2, K^+ 2.87, Rb^+ 2.75, Cs^+ 2.54 and NO_3^- 1.39. The solvated Li_3^+ has almost the same size as that of the Bu_4N^+ ion (tetrabutylammonium ion).

CONDUCTANCE measurements provide an insight into ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions in electrolyte solutions. Ramgopal and Jha¹ have determined the solvation numbers of some alkali metal ions from transport number measurements of KBr in DMSO and from the conductance data of alkali metal salts in DMSO reported in literature. High precision conductance data of alkali metal nitrates in non-aqueous solvents especially in DMSO are not available in literature. In this work the association constants, the extent of solvation and solvation numbers of the alkalimetal and nitrate ions have been determined from conductance data of high precision ($\pm 0.02\%$).

Experimental

DMSO (A.R. grade) was purified by vacuum fractionation². The middle fraction was repeatedly fractionated till the specific conductance of the final product was $2-3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The purified solvent was stored in a dry box in an atmosphere of pure dry N_2 . The water content determined by Karl Fischer titration was 0.001% by wt. The physical constants measured at 25° were: m.p., 18.55°; d., 1.0958 g cm^{-3} ; sp. cond., $2-3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; Diel. const., 46.6. The values reported in literature³ are m.p., 18.55°; d., 1.096 g cm^{-3} ; sp. cond., $3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; Diel. const., 46.6.

The alkali metal nitrates (AnalaR) were purified by repeated recrystallisation from conductance water. They were all dried in vacuo at 120°. The purity was determined by gravimetric analysis of the metal content⁴. The purity in all cases was better than 99.98%.

The direct current technique developed by Gunning and Gordon⁵ was employed for the conductance measurement. A modified Gordon cell in

conjunction with the liquid junction probe chambers devised by Elias and Schiff⁶ were used. A solution of 0.01 N KCl in methanol was used as the probe solution. The measurements were made during the winter season at night when the ambient temperature was well below 25°. The temperature regulation of the order $25.0 \pm 0.005^\circ$ was obtained in a thermostatic bath which contained about 30 litres of light transformer oil. Thermo regulation was effected by a highly sensitive electronic relay. Details of the experimental procedure were as given by Unni *et al.*⁷.

Results and Discussion

The conductance data are given in Table 1.

The Fuoss-Onsager-Skinner conductance equation⁸ has been used to analyse the data. Since the maximum concentration studied is only about 10^{-2} equiv. l^{-1} , γ is assumed to be unity and the equation suggested by the authors for dilute solutions has been used. The equation has the form

$$\Delta = \Delta_0 - Sc^{\frac{1}{2}} + E' c \ln (6E'_1 c) + Lc - A\Delta_0 cf^2 \dots (1)$$

where $A = K_A$. All the terms have been described by the authors of the equation. A function Δ' can be defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta' &= \Delta + Sc^{\frac{1}{2}} - E' c \ln (6E'_1 c) \\ &= \Delta_0 + (L - Af^2\Delta_0)c \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

A plot of Δ' against c should be linear with slope $L - A\Delta_0 f^2$ and intercept Δ_0 . An approximate initial value of Δ_0 obtained from a Shedlovsky plot was used to calculate the initial values of Δ' . Δ_0 and slopes were calculated by least mean square analysis. The refined values of Δ_0 were used to recalculate Δ' . The least mean square analysis

TABLE 1.—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES OF ALKALI METAL NITRATES IN DMSO AT 25°C AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS (c in equiv. l⁻¹, Λ in ohm⁻¹ cm² equiv.⁻¹)

LiNO ₃		NaNO ₃		KNO ₃		RbNO ₃		CsNO ₃	
c × 10 ⁴	Λ								
4.637	37.130	6.289	39.106	4.508	40.122	5.500	40.361	5.001	41.044
17.212	36.099	9.734	38.732	8.112	39.678	8.097	40.054	10.000	40.513
22.089	35.840	15.052	38.266	14.060	39.136	17.658	39.245	18.854	39.840
29.246	35.510	25.000	37.574	23.956	38.443	27.500	38.610	30.001	39.236
35.940	35.251	36.036	36.951	31.922	38.000	34.999	38.218	38.766	38.830
47.290	34.882	40.972	36.709	42.463	37.480	39.345	38.023	50.003	38.397
54.908	34.661	49.564	36.313	51.122	37.100	49.510	37.572	60.688	38.030
63.840	34.444	60.251	35.875	58.807	36.800	62.039	37.107	70.506	37.751
72.021	34.250	67.240	35.610	66.830	36.511	72.501	36.746	76.066	37.614
81.010	34.076	75.690	35.317	73.465	36.297	85.498	36.342	82.508	37.440

was repeated till the Δ_0 and the slope did not vary by more than 0.01%.

If it is assumed that $f^2 \approx 1$ for dilute solutions, the slope becomes $(L - A\Delta_0)$. The contact distances are determined by solving the equation,

$$(L - A\Delta_0) = E_1' \Delta_0 H(b) - E_2' G(b) - 6E'K(b) \dots (3)$$

where $b = e^2/aDkT$. The values of the functions $H(b)$, $G(b)$ and $K(b)$ are available in literature⁹. Trial values of 'b' are used to calculate $(L - A\Delta_0)$. From a plot of $(L - A\Delta_0)$ vs b, the 'b' corresponding to the experimental value of $(L - A\Delta_0)$ was interpolated. 'a' the ion size parameter was calculated from

$$a = e^2/bDkT = 560.47 \times 10^{-9}/bD \dots (4)$$

From the 'a' values K_A were calculated using the function⁹

$$K_A = 2.523 \times 10^{-10} \times a^{1/2} e^b \dots (5)$$

The values of 'a' and K_A are given in Table 2.

 TABLE 2—VALUES OF Δ_0 , a AND K_A OF ALKALI METAL NITRATES IN DMSO AT 25°C

Salt	Δ_0	$\frac{a}{\text{\AA}}$	K_A	Sum. cryst. radii in $\text{\AA}$
LiNO ₃	38.3	4.112	3.260	1.81
NaNO ₃	40.39	3.083	3.652	2.16
KNO ₃	41.36	3.246	3.506	2.54
RbNO ₃	41.74	3.331	3.449	2.69
CsNO ₃	42.34	3.360	3.330	2.90

Solvated radii and solvation numbers of alkali metal and nitrate ions :

From the limiting single ion conductances of the alkali metal and nitrate ions obtained from the conductance data¹⁰ the Stokes' radii (r_s) of the ions have been calculated. To obtain the corrected value, r_{Hx} , the method suggested by Nightingale¹¹ was employed. From a plot of r_s vs r_c (crystallographic radii) of the tetra alkyl ammonium ions¹²

which are assumed to be unsolvated the actual radii r_{Hx} of the smaller ions in DMSO were interpolated from their r_s values. From the corrected radii (r_{Hx}) and the crystallographic radii (r_c) of the alkali metal and nitrate ions the solvation numbers were calculated¹. The limiting single ion conductances, solvation numbers, r_c , r_s and r_{Hx} are given in Table 3. The plot of r_s vs r_c is shown in Fig. 1.

 Fig. 1. Plot of Crystallographic radii (r_c) vs Stokes' radii (r_s)

 TABLE 3—VALUES OF $\lambda_0^{\pm}$; r_s , r_c , r_{Hx} (in $\text{\AA}$) AND SOLVATION NUMBERS OF ALKALI METAL AND NITRATE IONS IN DMSO

Ion	$\lambda_0^{\pm}$	r_s	r_c	r_{Hx}	Solvation number
Li ⁺	11.80	3.486	0.60	4.78	4.30
Na ⁺	14.09	2.919	0.95	4.34	3.20
K ⁺	14.86	2.768	1.35	4.22	2.87
Rb ⁺	15.24	2.699	1.48	4.18	2.75
Cs ⁺	15.84	2.596	1.69	4.10	2.54
NO ₃ ⁻	26.50	1.552	1.20	3.33	1.39

It is clear that the extent of solvation is more for the cations than for the anion. This may be due to the stronger electrostatic interaction between the negative oxygen end of the S-O dipole of the DMSO molecule and the cation. It is reported that in dipolar aprotic solvents anions are only poorly solvated¹³. In DMSO the positive S centre is shielded by the two methyl groups and the steric hindrance thus reduces the solvation of anions through the S atom. Solvation decreases as r_c increases. It may be pointed out that the solvation number obtained for the Li^+ ion is greater than the value reported from NMR studies by Maxey and Popov¹⁴. The reason may be that the NMR method is sensitive only to the solvent molecules co-ordinated in the inner solvation sphere as reported by Streblov and Schneider¹⁵. Solvation numbers obtained in this work differ slightly from those reported by Ramgopal¹. This may be due to the difference in the methods followed for the estimation of the single ion conductances. The extent of solvation is in the order

Table 2 shows that the 'a' values are greater than the sum of the crystallographic radii for all the salts indicating the existence of solvation. The extent of solvation is greatest in the case of Li^+ ion, assuming that the NO_3^- ion is least solvated. The solvation numbers testify to this conclusion.

The K_A values which are a measure of ion-ion interaction are in the order $\text{NaNO}_3 > \text{KNO}_3 > \text{RbNO}_3 > \text{CsNO}_3 > \text{LiNO}_3$. The low K_A value of LiNO_3 may be ascribed to the lowered coulombic attraction of the solvated Li^+ ion caused by the large size of its solvo-dynamic unit (approximately equal to that of the Bu_4N^+ ion). Ion-pair formation is thus considerably reduced. From NaNO_3

to CsNO_3 even though the K_A values decrease, the differences are not much pronounced. This may be due to the almost near equal solvation members of these ions.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Principal, Regional Engineering College, Calicut for providing the necessary laboratory facilities.

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